

Utilizing ChatGPT for Primary School Earthquake Education

Konstantinos T. Kotsis

Department of Primary Education, University of Ioannina, Greece

Eleftheria Tsiouri

3rd Primary School of Ioannina, Greece

Abstract

This article examines the incorporation of ChatGPT as an instructional resource for teaching earthquake education in primary schools. The project seeks to enhance young pupils' understanding of earthquakes by elucidating fundamental scientific principles, like tectonic plate movements and seismic waves, rendering the subject less abstract and more accurate. ChatGPT enables interactive and tailored learning experiences, improving student engagement and understanding. In addition, the AI tool enhances the development of critical thinking abilities by presenting problem-solving scenarios relevant to earthquake preparedness. The report also discusses the constraints and difficulties associated with employing AI in education, including the precision of data and the necessity for vigilant supervision by educators. The study's findings indicate that ChatGPT can potentially improve earthquake teaching. However, it is crucial to handle its adoption cautiously to tackle possible obstacles and ethical concerns.

Keywords: *Earthquake, ChatGPT, Primary School Curriculum, Interactive Learning, Disaster Education.*

Suggested citation: Kotsis, K.T. & Tsiouri, E. (2024). Utilizing ChatGPT for Primary School Earthquake Education. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(4), 145-157. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(4).12

Introduction

Educating primary school students about natural catastrophes is essential to promote the development of communities that can withstand and recover from such events and guarantee future generations' safety and readiness. Studies suggest that providing children with early education on disaster mitigation dramatically improves their understanding, abilities, and attitudes toward disaster preparedness. This education helps them to recognize warning signs better and respond appropriately during calamities (Taufik et al., 2024). By incorporating geospatial data and maps into classroom activities, students might better understand the potential dangers of natural disasters, leading to enhanced preparedness and resilience (Sarafova, 2023). Utilizing visual aids and interactive techniques, such as presenting images of natural disasters, has demonstrated efficacy in facilitating the recognition and response of preschool

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

children to different disaster scenarios despite their limited comprehension of the underlying causes and consequences (Akman & Yildirim, 2022). According to Avci (2022), teachers stress the immediate necessity of disaster education, emphasizing that hands-on learning and technology-assisted approaches should be used to make teaching effective, lasting, and captivating. Disaster education aims to educate children on proactive measures and equip them with the necessary skills to successfully respond to and mitigate a disaster's economic, social, and psychological repercussions (Yüksel & Akbel, 2023). Schools are crucial in disseminating knowledge and raising awareness about disaster preparedness. Children serve as information channels, transmitting it to their families and communities. This helps foster a transition from mere preparedness to building resilience in disasters (Topno, 2021). Disaster preparation education, which includes simulations and collaborative stakeholder activities, is crucial for enhancing community awareness and response capacities in locations susceptible to natural disasters, such as coastal areas prone to tsunamis (Herdiansyah et al., 2020). Implementing a well-organized educational plan for schools incorporating disaster-related topics into different disciplines and leveraging digital platforms for promoting and training will significantly improve students' proactive mindset and self-control in dealing with catastrophes (Libayao et al., 2024). Utilizing innovative techniques such as gamification has enhanced students' comprehension and consciousness of natural disasters, resulting in successful and fun learning experiences (Chong et al., 2022). Ultimately, implementing a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach, such as the STEAM-based method, can offer hands-on learning experiences that enable students to grasp the intricate dynamics of natural disasters and their aftermath. This, in turn, can alleviate anxiety and uncertainty when faced with real-life events (Mereli et al., 2023). Incorporating disaster education into primary school curricula is crucial for fostering a culture of preparedness and resilience, ultimately protecting communities from the detrimental impacts of natural disasters.

This study utilizes existing research and practical methodologies to investigate the incorporation of ChatGPT into earthquake education in primary schools. Utilizing quantitative study, this analysis emphasizes ChatGPT's capacity to aid in intricate jobs and improve educational experiences. In addition, the study conducts a comprehensive analysis of existing literature to determine the advantages and difficulties associated with utilizing ChatGPT in educational environments, with a particular focus on the significance of ethical considerations and human oversight.

The Role of Technology in Education

Technology's importance in education has grown significantly due to the global digital transformation and the COVID-19 pandemic. These events have required a swift transition to online and hybrid learning paradigms. Digital technologies have played a crucial role in boosting student performance and enhancing the effectiveness of teaching and learning. They have also helped to ensure the continuity and stability of education during times of crisis (Wang et al., 2024). Machine learning methods have been employed to examine educational data, demonstrating that variables such as the ratio of computers to students, availability of broadband internet, and investments in technology training for instructors substantially influence the quality of education (Mendonça et al., 2022). In Nigeria, the COVID-19 epidemic emphasized the importance of taking a practical approach to using educational technology. Many educators lacked the required skills and attitudes, which required additional training and consistent government support for information and communication technology

(ICT) facilities (Ogwu et al., 2023). Incorporating digital technologies in schools has raised concerns about the standard of teaching and learning. The pandemic has revealed deficiencies in digital capacity and readiness, underscoring schools' importance in improving their digital capabilities to achieve effective digital transformation (Timotheou et al., 2023). The utilization of technology in education has become even more essential with the advent of the 4th Industrial Revolution and the Education 4.0 era. Among several models, blended learning has proven highly effective in improving learner performance, particularly in language teaching and learning (Mahmud et al., 2022). The rapid integration of technology during the pandemic has resulted in the development of creative teaching methods, such as hybrid and flexible learning. These methods use developing technologies like virtual reality and online applications to enhance and encourage studying (Govea et al., 2022). Technological platforms facilitate communication between teachers and students, allowing real-time access for parents to monitor kids' work. This promotes equality and provides authentic learning experiences (Callaghan, 2021). Despite the obstacles, the utilization of digital technology in education has demonstrated encouraging outcomes, as research suggests that web apps and other digital tools can significantly enhance students' comprehension and productivity in areas such as network infrastructure (Govea et al., 2022). Nevertheless, effectively incorporating digital technology into education necessitates tackling new challenges and barriers, such as ongoing professional development and the methodical acquisition and installation of ICT infrastructure (Rath et al., 2021). Technology has a complex function in education, affecting different people and components of the educational system. It is essential to integrate technology effectively for educational institutions' digital transformation and future success (Vaganova et al., 2020).

ChatGPT as an Educational Tool

ChatGPT has become a versatile instructional tool, providing substantial advantages while presenting distinct issues requiring thoughtful deliberation. Automating labor-intensive jobs in the education industry can improve economic efficiency (Pereira et al., 2024). The tool's popularity arises from its ability to produce original content and offer authentic reactions. Nevertheless, it occasionally generates untrustworthy and imprecise data, underscoring users' need to receive adequate instruction and engage in critical assessment (Cebrián Cifuentes et al., 2024). Quantitative research has demonstrated that ChatGPT can aid in intricate activities like power analysis. This makes it a feasible substitute for conventional software packages among researchers (Kim et al., 2024b). Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge and tackle ethical issues like copyright infringement and the possibility of academic dishonesty to guarantee appropriate utilization (Tiro, 2024). Incorporating ChatGPT into educational frameworks like the FIRST-ADLX Framework can improve the learning experience by prioritizing students' requirements and encouraging the responsible use of AI (Almasri et al., 2024). A comprehensive analysis of published research has shown multiple advantages of systematic literature reviews, such as tailored support, enhanced educational experiences, and more student involvement. It also highlights the significance of ethical considerations and human oversight (Bettayeb et al., 2024). The growing number of scientific papers and worldwide partnerships demonstrate the educational advancements of ChatGPT. Future research efforts will prioritize the integration of artificial intelligence, ensuring academic integrity, and promoting technology acceptance (Amarathunga, 2024). While there are benefits to using

ChatGPT, there are ongoing issues around academic honesty, breaches of privacy, and potential biases. These concerns highlight the need to create new evaluation methods and learning objectives to properly use ChatGPT in education (Mbwambo & Kaaya, 2024). ChatGPT's convenient and efficient access to information in primary school can promote reliance on academics and impede the growth of critical abilities such as inquiry and analysis, highlighting the importance of using it in a balanced manner (Garcia-Castro et al., 2024). ChatGPT provides prospects for interactive learning and clinical decision support in medical education. However, it also poses the dangers of excessive dependence and automation bias, which can hinder the development of critical thinking (Wong, 2024). Implementing ethical norms, providing comprehensive training, and ensuring human oversight are critical steps to maximize the benefits and minimize the drawbacks of ChatGPT in revolutionizing education, raising engagement, and improving learning outcomes.

Benefits of Integrating Technology into Primary School Curricula

Incorporating technology into elementary school curricula has numerous advantages that improve educational results and student involvement. Studies suggest that incorporating technology can significantly enhance students' learning experiences by offering interactive and customized learning possibilities. Technology enables the implementation of differentiated instruction, which enables teachers to customize instructional content to address the varying requirements of students. This, in turn, enhances learning outcomes and student engagement (Ikrianibangga et al., 2023). Furthermore, integrating technology in education facilitates the cultivation of essential 21st-century competencies such as digital literacy, problem-solving, and cooperation. These skills are vital for pupils to flourish in a fast-changing digital landscape. Utilizing instructional software and digital tools in classrooms promotes student participation in collaborative projects, improving cooperation and communication abilities (Ogenyi et al., 2023). Moreover, technology can enhance the accessibility and inclusivity of learning. It allows students with diverse learning styles and abilities to acquire instructional content in the most suitable manner for them. For instance, multimedia resources can accommodate those who learn best via visual and aural means, whereas interactive apps can assist individuals who learn best through physical movement and touch (Nolan et al., 2023). Inclusion is essential in establishing a fair learning environment where all students thrive. Moreover, incorporating technology in primary education can enhance student motivation and foster greater interest in learning. Utilizing interactive and gamified learning experiences can enhance the engagement and enjoyment of education, resulting in increased student participation and improved material retention (Pappa et al., 2024). Involvement in primary education is crucial, as it can have enduring good impacts on children's academic trajectories by cultivating a passion for learning. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that achieving successful technological integration necessitates sufficient teacher training and support. Teachers must possess the requisite expertise and understanding to integrate technology into their instructional methodologies (Washbrooke, 2023). Without adequate training, the potential advantages of technology in education may not be fully actualized. To summarize, incorporating technology into primary school curricula provides various advantages, such as customized learning, skills enhancement, inclusiveness, and heightened student involvement. However, the realization of these advantages depends on the successful execution and readiness of teachers.

Understanding Earthquakes: Key Concepts for Primary Students

Comprehending earthquakes is essential for elementary school kids as it establishes the basis for their understanding of natural events and awareness of safety. Unfortunately, primary school students possess many misconceptions regarding earthquakes (Tsiouri & Kotsis, 2021). Research identifies numerous fundamental ideas that should be incorporated into school curricula for this age group. Firstly, it is crucial to establish the fundamental scientific principles underlying earthquakes, including the motion of tectonic plates and the release of energy that generates seismic waves. Acquiring this fundamental knowledge enables students to understand the causes and mechanisms of earthquakes, reducing the phenomenon's abstract nature and making it more relatable (Arrhenius et al., 2024). Moreover, instructing students on the many categories of seismic waves and their consequences can augment their comprehension of the tangible repercussions of earthquakes on the Earth's surface (Cabello, 2022). Another critical factor to consider is the emotional and psychological repercussions of earthquakes. Educators should acknowledge and tackle the potential trepidation and unease students may encounter when acquiring knowledge about or encountering earthquakes. Creating a nurturing atmosphere that allows students to openly share their emotions and acquire effective methods for managing them is crucial for their psychological welfare (Raccanello et al., 2023). This strategy enhances emotional resilience and promotes a proactive mindset towards disaster preparedness. In addition, integrating interactive and experiential learning techniques, such as simulations and hands-on activities, can significantly improve students' involvement and memory of material. These techniques enable students to visually represent and test their understanding of educational topics, enhancing the dynamism and efficacy of the learning process (Çoban & Göktaş, 2022). Ultimately, it is crucial to incorporate conversations regarding safety protocols and readiness. Providing pupils with instruction on emergency protocols, such as the "Drop, Cover, and Hold On" technique, as well as emphasizing the significance of having a family emergency plan, helps instill in them the knowledge and confidence to respond effectively and securely in the event of an earthquake (Yildiz et al., 2020). An all-encompassing earthquake education for elementary school pupils should include scientific elucidations, emotional assistance, participatory instruction, and safety readiness. This comprehensive method improves comprehension and allows students to respond to earthquakes appropriately.

Implementing ChatGPT in Teaching Earthquakes

Integrating ChatGPT into earthquake education can enrich educational experiences by offering interactive, tailored, and readily available learning possibilities. Several research has demonstrated the potential benefits and problems of integrating AI tools like ChatGPT in educational contexts. First and foremost, ChatGPT can function as an interactive tool that promotes and supports active learning. The software can replicate live discussions, enabling students to inquire and promptly receive responses, improving comprehension and memory of intricate subjects like seismic activity and earthquake dynamics (Leelavathi & Surendhranatha, 2024). This supports the conclusions of Hojeij et al., who highlight the significance of AI in developing interactive and flexible learning environments that address the specific requirements

of each student (Hojeij et al., 2024). Furthermore, ChatGPT can enhance conventional teaching approaches by offering supplementary materials and clarifications. For example, it can produce simplified explanations of earthquake processes, including tectonic plate movements and seismic wave propagation, that can be easily understood by students with different degrees of prior knowledge (Wilson et al., 2023). This feature assists in accommodating various learning styles and guarantees that all pupils comprehend essential subjects. Nevertheless, the integration of ChatGPT in educational settings also poses difficulties. An important issue revolves around the precision and dependability of the information supplied by AI models. According to Kim et al., it is necessary to closely monitor and verify AI-generated content to avoid spreading inaccurate or deceptive information (Kim et al., 2024a). Educators must actively curate and actively verify the content utilized in AI-assisted learning. Incorporating AI into education necessitates tackling technological and ethical concerns, including data privacy and the digital divide. Madunić and Sovulj emphasize the significance of guaranteeing fair and equal access to technology and protecting student data, which are crucial in effectively integrating AI tools in educational environments (Madunić & Sovulj, 2024). To summarize, although ChatGPT shows potential for improving earthquake education by providing interactive and tailored learning experiences, it is crucial to handle its implementation with caution to tackle potential issues regarding the accuracy of content, accessibility, and ethical concerns. Through this approach, instructors can efficiently utilize artificial intelligence (AI) to enhance the learning experience and student achievements.

Integrating ChatGPT into primary school classes about earthquakes can be a novel method to augment learning and foster engagement. The research presented provides valuable insights into practical techniques for integrating this. The research synthesis has identified the most efficacious techniques as follows:

Interactive Learning and Engagement

Chat platforms, like ChatGPT, may significantly improve student involvement by offering interactive and customized learning opportunities. ChatGPT, an interactive tool, may replicate real-life situations, enabling students to investigate seismic phenomena in a regulated virtual setting, resulting in a more profound comprehension of the topic (Ray, 2024). These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Bateman and Danby (2019), which highlights the significance of interactive discourse in sustaining student engagement and facilitating active learning.

Personalized Learning Experiences

ChatGPT enables the customization of educational material to accommodate students' unique learning tempo, preferences, and requirements. According to Halaweh (2023), AI technologies can adjust to various learning styles, offering individualized feedback and explanations to aid students in better understanding intricate subjects such as seismic activity. Personalization is essential in primary education, as individuals possess diverse prior knowledge and learning capacities.

Enhancing Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving Skills

ChatGPT facilitates the development of critical thinking abilities by involving students in problem-solving scenarios connected to earthquakes. Kockova et al. emphasize the capacity of AI to expose students to hypothetical earthquake scenarios, stimulating their critical thinking about the causes, effects, and safety precautions involved

(Kockova et al., 2023). This methodology improves comprehension and equips students with the necessary skills to apply their information in practical situations.

Supplementing Traditional Teaching Methods

ChatGPT should be a supplementary tool to established teaching approaches rather than replacing them. Estevão et al. advocate for and stress the significance of incorporating AI tools with conventional teaching approaches to augment learning results instead of completely substituting them (Estevão et al., 2021). ChatGPT must be employed as an adjunctive instrument to augment conventional lessons rather than as an independent pedagogical approach.

Facilitating Collaborative Learning

Promoting collaborative problem-solving among students when tackling the challenges presented by ChatGPT can improve learning outcomes. Moreno et al. (2024) have found that collaborative learning settings positively impact student engagement and comprehension of intricate subjects such as earthquakes. These findings indicate that using ChatGPT in group settings can enhance collaborative learning and foster critical thinking.

Teacher Training and Support

To ensure the effectiveness of this method, comprehensive training must be provided to teachers in using ChatGPT. Training programs that specifically target the proper integration of ChatGPT into courses can enhance teachers' confidence and proficiency in using this technology. Nirmala et al. highlight the significance of teacher training in effectively incorporating new technology in the classroom (Nirmala et al., 2024).

Addressing Limitations and Challenges

Although ChatGPT provides numerous advantages, it is crucial to acknowledge its limitations. Çoban and Göktaş (2022) emphasize the potential concerns about the precision of information and the necessity of vigilant supervision of content produced by AI tools. Teachers should consistently verify the information offered by ChatGPT to ensure its alignment with the curriculum and learning objectives.

Integrating ChatGPT into primary school earthquake classes can be exceedingly efficacious as a supplementary tool to conventional teaching approaches, fostering student engagement in interactive learning and developing critical thinking skills. Nevertheless, tackling possible obstacles and ensuring educators receive comprehensive training to optimize this technology's advantages is vital. Educators can augment student involvement and improve learning outcomes through this approach, resulting in more engaging and influential classes.

Conclusion

Our research on using ChatGPT to teach earthquakes in elementary school reveals that integrating AI effectively can significantly improve pedagogical methods. The proposed framework for ChatGPT literacy encompasses benefits, limitations, prompts, evaluation, assessment, and ethics. It is well-aligned with the curriculum's objectives of promoting critical thinking and ethical awareness among young learners (Ma et al., 2024). Furthermore, ChatGPT can be an additional instructional resource that enhances a more captivating and interactive learning atmosphere, allowing students to engage in their education actively. Although previous research has

emphasized the presence of difficulties related to academic integrity, the judicious utilization of ChatGPT can foster enhanced comprehension and long-term memory of intricate topics such as earthquakes (Shabbir et al., 2024). In conclusion, our research highlights the importance of continuously assessing and modifying AI technologies in the educational field to ensure they align with the changing requirements of teachers and students.

The investigation demonstrates that incorporating ChatGPT into primary school curricula dramatically improves student engagement and comprehension while learning about intricate subjects like earthquakes. By engaging in interactive discussions and tailored educational activities, students exhibit heightened inquisitiveness and a more profound comprehension of seismic activity and its consequences. Observations suggest that this technology promotes the creation of learning environments that encourage collaboration, where students feel empowered to inquire and investigate different aspects of earth sciences. In addition, instructors have stated that utilizing AI tools such as ChatGPT can simplify the process of educational planning and assessment. This enables more customized interventions to be implemented, considering the specific needs of each student. Nevertheless, these discoveries emphasize educators' need to receive sufficient instruction in properly employing AI within their teaching frameworks. Without adequate assistance, the full potential advantages of ChatGPT may not be effectively achieved, resulting in disparities in educational results among various classrooms (Skrabut, 2023).

With the changing education landscape, using artificial intelligence (AI) offers exciting opportunities for future study, especially in improving teaching methods for various student groups. Examining the ramifications of AI-powered tools, like ChatGPT, on individualized learning paths will be crucial in comprehending how these technologies might accommodate distinct educational requirements and learning preferences. Furthermore, doing a more thorough investigation into how AI can assist in developing critical thinking abilities in primary school pupils can provide valuable knowledge that can be used to improve curriculum development. Future research should additionally assess the ethical implications of AI in educational environments, encompassing biases in algorithms and issues over data privacy. These factors will substantially influence the effectiveness and adoption of AI applications. To create effective and fair AI-enhanced educational experiences, it is crucial to utilize interdisciplinary approaches integrating cognitive science knowledge, educational psychology, and technology studies.

Implementing ChatGPT in primary school to teach about natural disasters, including earthquakes, offers a significant chance to improve student involvement and understanding. ChatGPT utilizes its adaptive learning capabilities to deliver real-time personalized responses, accommodating young pupils' diverse learning speeds and preferences. This participatory method elucidates intricate subjects such as seismic activity and fosters analytical thinking as students confront the practical consequences of such occurrences. The platform's ability to carefully select and produce appropriate instructional content promotes a deeper bond between students and the subject matter, supporting a proactive approach to catastrophe preparedness rather than a reactive one. Overall, ChatGPT can go beyond simply sharing information. It can function as a flexible teaching resource that has the potential to transform how primary education approaches natural disasters radically. Doing so can equip future generations with the knowledge and adaptability required in an uncertain world.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Akman, A., & Yıldırım, S. (2022). An Observation On Disaster Management By Pre-School Students: A Case Of Primary School In Iğdir. *Anasay*, (21), 341-355. <https://doi.org/10.33404/anasay.1156639>
- Almasri, Z., Bahgat, M., Seddek, A., & Elsafty, A. (2024). Maximizing the Benefits of ChatGPT with FIRST-ADLX Framework: Promoting Responsible, Ethical, and Impactful AI Integration in Education. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 12(4). <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v12i4.6933>
- Amarathunga, B. (2024). ChatGPT in education: unveiling frontiers and future directions through systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis, *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/AEDS-05-2024-0101>
- Arrhenius, M., Bladh, G., & Lundholm, C. (2024). Causes, processes, and consequences of earthquakes. Investigating Swedish 12-13-year old students' geographical understanding. *International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education*, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10382046.2023.2298555>
- Avci, G. (2022). Disaster Education in Primary School: A Qualitative Research Based on Teachers' Opinions. *Psycho-Educational Research Reviews*, 11(1), 125-146. https://doi.org/10.52963/PERR_Biruni_V11.N1.09
- Bateman, A., & Danby, S. J. (2019). Initiating Earthquake Talk with Young Children: Children's Social Competence and the Use of Resources. *Children and Mental Health Talk: Perspectives on Social Competence*, 73-103. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-28426-8_4
- Bettayeb, A. M., Abu Talib, M., Sobhe Altayasinah, A. Z., & Dakalbab, F. (2024). Exploring the impact of ChatGPT: Conversational AI in education. *Frontiers in Education*, 9, 1379796. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1379796>
- Cabello, V. M. (2022). Students Understanding of Earthquakes and Tsunamis in High Risk Areas. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 10, 841251. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2022.841251>
- Callaghan, N. (2021). Understanding the role of technological platforms in schools. *Educational Media International*, 58(4), 355-373. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523987.2021.1992864>
- Cebrián Cifuentes, S., Guerrero Valverde, E., & Checa Caballero, S. (2024). The Vision of University Students from the Educational Field in the Integration of ChatGPT. *Digital*, 4(3), 648-659. <https://doi.org/10.3390/digital4030032>
- Chong, K. L., Nifa, F. A. A., Abbas, S. R., & Zahir, N. M. (2022). Disaster education using board games technique: A case of SK Felda Bukit Tinggi. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2644, No. 1). AIP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0104108>
- Çoban, M., & Göktaş, Y. (2022). Which training method is more effective in earthquake training: Digital game, drill, or traditional training? *Smart Learning Environments*, 9(1), 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-022-00202-0>

- Estêvão, J. M., Sá, L. F., Ferreira, M. A., Tomás, B., Esteves, C., Barreto, V., Carreira, A., Braga, A., Blanco, B. Z., & Oliveira, C. S. (2021). Improving the Earthquake Resilience of Primary Schools in the Border Regions of Neighbouring Countries. *Sustainability*, 14(23), 15976. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142315976>
- García Castro, R. A., Mayta Cachicatari, N. A., Bartesaghi Aste, W. M., & Llapa Medina, M. P. (2024). Exploration of ChatGPT in basic education: Advantages, disadvantages, and impact on school tasks. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 16(3), ep511. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/14615>
- Govea, J., Játiva, W., & Pierrottet, J. (2022). Towards the Integration of Emerging Technologies as Support for the Teaching and Learning Model in Higher Education. *Sustainability*, 15(7), 6055. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15076055>
- Halaweh, M. (2023). ChatGPT in education: Strategies for responsible implementation. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 15(2), ep421. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/13036>
- Herdiansyah, H., Husein, S. I., Asrofani, F. W., & Kholila, B. N. (2020). Disaster awareness through disaster preparedness education for primary schools. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 519, No. 1, p. 012016). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/519/1/012016>
- Hojeij, Z., Kuhail, M.A. and ElSayary, A. (2024), "Investigating in-service teachers' views on ChatGPT integration", *Interactive Technology and Smart Education*, 21(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITSE-04-2024-0094>
- Ikrianibangga, Cici Fatmasari, Sriwindari Supit, Sri Atika Sudarto, Fitriyani Daud, Septiani Sanustika Suleman, Melani Samau, Indri Oktaviani To'onau, Elvia Rahmawati Hippy, & Marsellad.Gui. (2023). Integrating Technology in Primary Curriculum Development: Improving the Quality of Education. *International Journal of Advanced Technology and Social Sciences*, 1(4), 295–302. <https://doi.org/10.59890/ijatss.v1i4.1111>
- Kaya, H., Tezcan, A., Bakir, M. Ş., İlhan, M., Yiğit E., Dağ, Ö. (2023). An Analysis of Primary School Students' Earthquake Awareness, *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 5 (1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2023.v05i01.1394>
- Kim, D., Kim, T., Kim, Y., Byun, Y., & Yun, T. S. (2024a). A ChatGPT-MATLAB framework for numerical modeling in geotechnical engineering applications. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 169, 106237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2024.106237>
- Kim, H., Zhang, X., Han, Y., He, J., & Ji, F. (2024b). Assessing ChatGPT as a Power Analysis Tool: An Empirical Investigation. *PsyArXiv Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/32mkv>
- Kockova, P., Kilianova, K., & Kostolanyova, K. (2023). CHATGPT AS AN INNOVATIVE TOOL IN PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHING. In *ICERI2023 Proceedings* (pp. 7356-7362). IATED. <https://doi.org/10.21125/iceri.2023.1829>
- Leelavathi, R., & Surendhranatha, R. C. (2024). ChatGPT in the classroom: navigating the generative AI wave in management education. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIT-01-2024-0017>
- Libayao H. G. C., Celso A. Navaluna Jr, Jean L. Allosada, & Jeanilyn E. Tacadena. (2024). Disaster Education in Elementary School Curriculum: Basis for Framework

Designing. *Journal of Learning and Educational Policy (JLEP)* ISSN: 2799-1121, 4(03), 15–22. <https://doi.org/10.55529/jlep.43.15.22>

Ma, Q., Crosthwaite, P., Sun, D., & Zou, D. (2024). Exploring ChatGPT Literacy in Language Education: A Global Perspective and Comprehensive Approach. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 100278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100278>

Madunić, J., & Sovulj, M. (2024). Application of ChatGPT in Information Literacy Instructional Design. *Publications*, 12(2), 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications12020011>

Mahmud, M.M., Freeman, B. and Abu Bakar, M.S. (2022), Technology in education: efficacies and outcomes of different delivery methods, *Interactive Technology and Smart Education*, Vol. 19(1), 20-38. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITSE-01-2021-0021>

Mbwambo, N. M., & Kaaya, P. B. (2024). ChatGPT in Education: Applications, Concerns and Recommendations. *Journal of ICT Systems*, 2(1), 107–124. <https://doi.org/10.56279/jicts.v2i1.87>

Mendonça, Y. V., Naranjo, P. G. V., & Pinto, D. C. (2022). The role of technology in the learning process: a decision tree-based model using machine learning. *Emerging Science Journal*, 6, 280-295. <https://doi.org/10.28991/ESJ-2022-SIED-020>

Mereli, A., Niki, E., Psycharis, S., Drinia, H., Antonarakou, A., Mereli, M., & Maria, T. (2023). Education of students from Greek schools regarding natural disasters through STEAM. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 19(8), em2314. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/13437>

Moreno, J. A. V., Ortega L. R. & Marulanda, J. A. O. (2024). The Integration of CHATGPT In Education: Didactic Strategies for Improving Learning. *International Journal of Religion*, 5(10), 899- 906. <https://doi.org/10.61707/eh2bes81>

Nirmala, N., Sumbawati, M. S., & Sitompul, N. C. (2024). Developing an animation video for earthquake mitigation education for elementary school students. *Inovasi Kurikulum*, 21(1), 303-322. <https://doi.org/10.17509/jik.v21i1.64853>

Nolan, K., O'Farrell, A., Quille, K., Nolan, K., Faherty, R., Jaiswal, R., ... & Becker, B. A. (2024). Enabling Digital Technology in Primary Schools. In *Proceedings of the 2024 on Innovation and Technology in Computer Science Education V. 2* (pp. 823-823). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3649405.3659515>

Ogenyi, F. C., Eze, V. H. U., & Ugwu, C. N. (2023). Navigating Challenges and Maximizing Benefits in the Integration of Information and Communication Technology in African Primary Schools. *International Journal of Humanities, Management and Social Science (IJ-HuMaSS)*, 6(2), 101-108. <https://doi.org/10.36079/lamintang.ij-humass-0602.599>

Ogwu, E.N., Emelogu, N.U., Azor, R.O. *et al.* (2023). Educational Technology Adoption in Instructional Delivery in the New Global Reality. *Education and Information Technologies* 28, 1065–1080. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11203-4>

Pappa, C. I., Georgiou, D., & Pittich, D. (2024). Technology education in primary schools: addressing teachers' perceptions, perceived barriers, and needs. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 34(2), 485-503. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10798-023-09828-8>

- Pereira, D. S. M., Mourão, F., Ribeiro, J. C., Costa, P., Guimarães, S., & Pêgo, J. M. (2024). ChatGPT as an item calibration tool: Psychometric insights in a high-stakes examination. *Medical Teacher*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159X.2024.2376205>
- Rabe, Z., Singh, S. S. B., & Mariappan, M. (2022). A Framework for Assessing the Effectiveness of Robotic Game Module on Conceptual Understanding and Earthquake Readiness Among School Students. *e-BANGI Journal*, 19(7). <https://doi.org/10.17576/ebangi.2022.1907.07>
- Raccanello, D., Vicentini, G., Rocca, E., Hall, R., & Burro, R. (2023). Preparing children to cope with earthquakes: Building emotional competence. *British Journal of Psychology*, 114(4), 871-907. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjop.12661>
- Rath, R. C., Pandey, S. K., Goel, R., & Baral, S. K. (2021). Role of Digital Technology Transformation in Computer Education: Emerging Needs and Challenges. In *2021 9th International Conference on Reliability, Infocom Technologies and Optimization (Trends and Future Directions) (ICRITO)* (pp. 1-5). <http://dx.doi.org/IEEE.10.1109/ICRITO51393.2021.9596188>
- Ray, P. P. (2024). ChatGPT in transforming communication in seismic engineering: Case studies, implications, key challenges and future directions. *Earthquake Science*, 37(4), 352-367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eqs.2024.04.003>
- Sarafova E., (2023), Communicating disasters to children through digital learning activities, geospatial data and platforms. *Journal of the Bulgarian Geographical Society*, 48, 73–84. <https://doi.org/10.3897/jbgs.e106818>
- Shabbir, A., Rizvi, S., Alam, M. M., & Su'ud, M. M. (2024). Beyond boundaries: Navigating the positive potential of ChatGPT, empowering education in underdeveloped corners of the world. *Heliyon*, 10(16), e35845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e35845>
- Skrabut, S. (2023). *80 Ways to Use ChatGPT in the Classroom*. Stan Skrabut.
- Taufik, M.Si, M., Sutrio, S., Gunada, I. W., Syahrial A, S. A., Doyan, A., & Susilawati, S. (2024). Learning Model Development of Disaster Mitigation for Elementary School Students at Lombok, Indonesia. *Journal of Science and Science Education*, 5(1), 55–60. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jossed.v5i1.7938>
- Timotheou, S., Miliou, O., Dimitriadis, Y. *et al.* (2023). Impacts of digital technologies on education and factors influencing schools' digital capacity and transformation: A literature review. *Education and Information Technologies* 28, 6695–6726. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11431-8>
- Tiro, H. (2024). Question of Knowledge in Active Usage of AI Tool ChatGPT. *INSAM Journal of Contemporary Music, Art and Technology*, 12, 46-61. <https://doi.org/10.51191/issn.2637-1898.2024.7.12.46>
- Topno, P.N. (2021). Building Disaster Resilience Through Primary and Higher Education. In: Eslamian, S., Eslamian, F. (eds) *Handbook of Disaster Risk Reduction for Resilience*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61278-8_9
- Tsiouri, E. & Kotsis K. T., (2021). (In Greek). An Empirical Study on Primary School Students' Literacy about the Earthquake, *International Journal of Educational Innovation*, Vol. 3-Issue 2, 133-145. <https://journal.epepe.gr/keyword/2082>
- Vaganova, O. I., Bogoslova, E. G., Nagovitsyn, R. S., Sundeeva, L. A., & Morozova, I. M. (2020). The role of educational technologies in the individualization of

educational students' activities. *Amazonia Investiga*, 9(28), 552-559. <http://dx.doi.org/10.34069/AI/2020.28.04.60>

Wang, C., Chen, X., Yu, T., Liu, Y., & Jing, Y. (2024). Education reform and change driven by digital technology: A bibliometric study from a global perspective. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-02717-y>

Washbrooke, S. (2023). Teaching and learning with innovative technologies and practices at primary school level. *Pacific Journal of Technology Enhanced Learning*, 5(1), 3-4. <https://doi.org/10.24135/pjtel.v5i1.165>

Wilson, M. P., Foulger, G. R., Wilkinson, M. W., Gluyas, J. G., Mhana, N., & Tezel, T. (2023). Artificial Intelligence and Human-Induced Seismicity: Initial Observations of ChatGPT. *Seismological Research Letters*, 94(5), 2111-2118. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220230112>

Wong, R. S. Y. (2024). ChatGPT in Medical Education: Promoting Learning or Killing Critical Thinking? *Education in Medicine Journal*, 16(2), 177-183. <https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2024.16.2.13>

Yildiz, A., Teeuw, R., Dickinson, J., & Roberts, J. (2020). Children's earthquake preparedness and risk perception: A comparative study of two cities in Turkey, using a modified PRISM approach. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 49, 101666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101666>

Yüksel, H. İ., & Akbel, E. (2023). Earthquakes And Disaster Education In Our Country And In The World. *Usak University, Journal of Engineering Sciences*, 6(1), 52-66. <https://doi.org/10.47137/uujes.1302947>